

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Theyr

Using Explainable AI to Improve User
Trust and Adoption in Maritime Routing

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 Challenge overview

The Alan Turing Institute's Data Study Group (DSG) is a collaborative research hackathon, aimed at bringing multi-disciplinary researchers together to solve interesting real-world problems. In this DSG, Theyr, a commercial shipping voyage optimisation provider presented a challenge on trust and explainability of AI. Their product provides optimised voyage routes for ships to save fuel and time, but ship captains may decide not to follow the routes because they do not understand why the software chose a specific route. The aim of the challenge is to investigate how to interpret the decisions made by the software, and how to communicate that information to an end-user.

1.2 Data overview

Two datasets were provided by Theyr for the DSG. The first is a synthetic dataset of voyage routes containing a set of waypoints for each route. The waypoints determine the path for a vessel to follow, with features associated with each waypoint, such as the vessel's speed and weather conditions. The second is a real dataset containing email communications between a ship's captain and an onshore weather routing team. These are reports providing recommendations on heading, speed, and weather conditions to the captain.

1.3 Approaches

With a large team consisting of 11 researchers from diverse backgrounds, four sub-teams were formed to thoroughly cover each aspect of the challenge:

1. Identify which points on the voyage where an optimised route starts to differ from the standard route
2. Develop a method to find the important features of the optimised route
3. Generate reports to communicate the results to a ship captain

4. Evaluate the generated reports to ensure quality and accuracy

1.4 Key findings

The initial results found a few possible solutions to the challenge, but full experiments and validation of the results is required to definitively show the success of these methods.

Here are the key findings of the project:

- The distance between waypoints of two routes is a strong indicator for areas of interest on a voyage route. There is a clear distinction between waypoints identified within a segment of interest and waypoints outside of such segments.
- Machine learning models can be used to extract feature importance scores. Both a linear regression and a random forest model were successfully used to quantify the importance of each feature used.
- While retrieval augmented generation (RAG) can ensure large language models (LLMs) provide the correct data in terms of numbers and values, it is insufficient for a LLM to understand the meaning behind that data, leading to it retrieving the wrong data columns when queried by a user.
- Human reports where captain responses are always included and longer detailed routing descriptions are highly recommended to improve quality for training and evaluating AI-generated reports.

1.5 Recommendations and future work

While validation tests are necessary to confirm the results of the project, some insights and recommendations for future directions can already be drawn. A combined dataset with matching voyage data and email communications would be valuable for obtaining ground truth data. Similarly, including responses from captains would provide clarity on the quality of the reports provided by human weather routers. Ensemble methods for extracting feature importance could be explored by comparing machine learning models and analysing the strengths of each

model on different types of routes. Finally, it is recommended to explore other natural language processing methods, such as context-free grammars, rather than large language models, where outputs can be more strictly defined and controlled compared to the free-form interaction of LLMs.

2 Introduction

2.1 Background

Theyr Ltd. is a London-based solutions provider specialising in high-fidelity voyage optimisation and high-precision MetOcean data, with mechanisms for the analysis, delivery, and visualisation of this data.

Theyr's core product is T-VOS, the first AI-based multi-objective voyage optimisation software for the shipping industry, capable of simultaneously optimising for time, fuel, time charter equivalent (TCE—a shipping industry metric used to calculate average daily revenue), and emissions. It incorporates over a decade of academic research and development from the AI team at the University of Southampton, leading to a reduction of ships' emissions by over 5% above the current industry standard solution.

However, ship captains may be reluctant to follow the optimised voyages due to their own experiences and preferences, particularly in scenarios where they do not understand why the software has selected a specific route. Communicating such information in a way that is easily understood by captains is essential to increase both confidence in and uptake of autonomous systems. The main goal is to improve user confidence in the commercial software T-VOS, which will help further de-carbonise the shipping industry.

2.2 DSG Objectives

The aim of this challenge is to develop techniques to interpret the decisions made by T-VOS and communicate the reasons to the ship captains. There are three key objectives:

1. **Isolate which features impact the fuel and time efficiency of suggested routes**

Each route provided by T-VOS consists of a number of waypoints to guide a ship's captain. The heading and speed of the ship can change between waypoints to reflect fuel or time-efficient optimisation. For each waypoint along a route, weather and MetOcean data can influence the safety and performance of the vessel. While the overall performance in terms of fuel and time can be computed for the entire route, isolating which specific features caused the difference, and at which waypoints, is more challenging.

2. **Generate reports for ship captains based on the identified features of importance**

Once the relevant features for explaining the performance of optimised routes are found, this information must be communicated to ship captains. Typically, a formatted report is generated, showing the suggested route and explaining why the route should be taken. Potential solutions for generating such reports include a simple template, context-free grammar, or a more complex generative large language model.

3. **Develop an evaluation metric to assure the quality of generated reports**

An ideal solution for report generation could involve an interactive chatbot where ship captains can ask questions and request further clarification on aspects they are unsure about. However, safeguards and quality assurance measures must be implemented to prevent the system from providing incorrect information. An evaluation metric to assess the quality of generated responses would help in training the generative system and identifying when responses contain potentially false information.

3 Data overview

Two datasets were provided for the challenge: voyage route data and email communications. The voyage route data consists of numerical data

generated by T-VOS to describe a route, along with the associated waypoints and weather conditions. The email communications comprise natural language text data made up of email exchanges between shore-side weather routing teams and ship captains. The two sets of data are unrelated, meaning the voyages in the route data do not correspond to the voyages described in the email exchanges. Initial data exploration was conducted on the two datasets to learn about their properties and how they could be used.

3.1 Voyage route data

Voyage data is generated by Theyr from their T-VOS system. Each file describes a port-to-port route and consists of a set number of waypoints. Each row describes a single waypoint, and the columns detail the properties at that waypoint. The columns include data such as the longitude and latitude coordinates, fuel consumption, distance to the next waypoint, and MetOcean weather data. Each route is labelled based on the vessel, load, origin, and destination ports. There are:

- Two types of vessels (9999989 - Panamax Bulker, 9999982 - Handymax Tanker)
- Two loading conditions (Ballast, Laden)
- 20 unique ports

In total there are 200 optimised voyages for different vessels, loading conditions and ports. There are also 5000 un-optimised routes for a single voyage scenario, with the vessel 9999982 Handymax Tanker, Laden, from Vera Cruz to Nouadhibou.

Table 1 describes the columns found in the voyage data. While most of the data types are floating-point numbers, they all represent different units such as degrees, hours, or metric tons. We perform normalisation during the experiments as the ranges of data can vary even within the same unit. For example, the ocean current u and v components are typically less than 0.5, while the wind speed could range from 1 to 10 metres per second.

Name	Description	Datatype (units)
Longitude	longitude coordinate of the waypoint	Float
Latitude	latitude coordinate of the waypoint	Float
Timestamp	date and time when the vessel should reach the waypoint	String
Speed	speed of the vessel	Float (Knots)
Direction	current heading of the vessel	Float (Degrees)
Distance	distance from the current waypoint to the next waypoint	Float (Nautical miles)
Fuel consumption	amount of fuel consumed to travel to the next waypoint	Float (Metric tons)
Daily fuel consumption	the average daily fuel consumption	Float (Metric tons)
Duration	time taken to travel to the next waypoint	Float (Hours)
Wind, Wave, Ocean current direction	directions of weather conditions on the vessel	Float (degrees)
Wind and Ocean current speed	speed of the wind and ocean currents	Float (metres per second)
Wind and Ocean current U and V	u and v components of the wind and ocean currents	Float (metres per second)
Wave period	time period of the waves	Float (seconds)
Wave Height	height of the waves	Float (metres)
Is ECA	whether the waypoint is in an ECA (Emission Control Area) zone where a different type of fuel must be used	Boolean

Table 1: Overview of columns in voyage route data

3.1.1 Route segment analysis

The voyage data was analysed to understand the distribution of the number of waypoints per voyage. This helped to inform how the distributions might change when the voyage is separated into smaller segments and to identify the key relevant features. This process was useful when building the models.

Figure 1 shows the number of waypoints per voyage forms a non-uniform distribution. There are a few voyages that contain over 140 waypoints, but the majority contain fewer than 100 waypoints. The voyages can then be divided and categorised based on the number of waypoints.

Figure 1: Non-uniform distribution of the number of waypoints per voyage of the whole dataset.

In total, there are 76 voyages with less than 100 waypoints and 24 voyages with more than 140 waypoints. It is important to note that the

number of waypoints do not correlate to the distance of the voyage, as the distance between each waypoint can vary greatly. Figure 2 demonstrates this difference in distances between waypoints. The distances can vary from a minimum of two nautical miles (NM) to a maximum of over 200 nautical miles.

Figure 2: Distribution of the distance between waypoints of the whole dataset. Waypoints with distance lower than five miles were excluded for visualisation purpose.

While the majority of distances between waypoints fall between 100 and 150 nautical miles, there are also a number of waypoints with less than 20 nautical miles between them. These shorter distances can be explained as near-shore segments of a route, where tighter turns are needed to avoid land masses and follow traffic schemes.

3.1.2 Safety estimation

Safety estimation is useful to evaluate how close a vessel has been to its hard safety limits throughout the route. It impacts the safety of the crew, goods and the vessel itself. We investigate the safety limits of a vessel from three aspects: wave height, wind speed, and vessel maximum speed. For each segment of the voyage, we compute the *waveSafetyScore*, *windSafetyScore*, and *speedSafetyScore* as shown in Equations 1, 2 and 3 respectively. *overallSafetyScore* is the mean of wave, wind and speed scores. The higher the scores the safer it is.

$$waveSafetyScore = \frac{wv_{max} - wv}{wv_{max}} \quad (1)$$

where wv_{max} is the maximum safe wave height for the vessel and wv is the wave height at the current waypoint.

$$windSafetyScore = \frac{wd_{max} - wd}{wd_{max}} \quad (2)$$

where wd_{max} is the maximum safe wind speed for the vessel and wd is the wind speed at the current waypoint.

$$speedSafetyScore = \frac{s_{max} - s}{s_{max}} \quad (3)$$

where s_{max} is the maximum speed of the vessel and s is the current speed of the vessel.

Figure 3 shows the safety trends for two routes between Vera Cruz and Nouadhibou for laden vessel 89. The solid lines represent the route with minimum fuel usage (MinFuel) and the dashed lines represent the fastest route (MinTime). The blue line is for *speedSafetyScore*, the red line is for *waveSafetyScore* and the green line is for *windSafetyScore*. The vessel's speed is constant for both routes, but it travels faster on the MinTime route compared to the MinFuel route, as indicated by the blue lines. For this specific setting, the vessel is near its wind speed and wave height limits, as indicated by the high spikes in these lines for both routes.

Figure 3: Safety Estimation for a single MIN_TIME and MIN_FUEL route

Figure 4 shows the safety estimation for all the files filtered by MinTime and MinFuel routes. Overall, MinFuel routes are safer than MinTime routes. Averaged across all the files, wind and wave safety scores are consistently near the limits, as indicated by the high scores. In terms of speed, MinFuel routes are safer than MinTime routes. We also analysed all the files segregated by vessel and loading conditions, and no significant differences were found in the safety conditions.

3.1.3 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal component analysis (PCA) can be used to identify the major factors that contribute most to the fuel and time efficiency of shipping routes. This assumes that components with higher variance have a larger impact because they may cause more deviations along a route. For a single route, we analysed the key weather-related features to understand which of these had the most impact. For a single route, we took the key weather related features to understand which of these impacted the route most. Figure 5 shows the PCA results for one of the fuel-efficient routes. We note that the ocean current speed most impacts the route and

Figure 4: Safety Estimation for all MIN_TIME and MIN_FUEL routes

improves fuel consumption, while wind and wave direction have a negative impact and reduce fuel consumption.

3.2 Email communications

The email communications are extracted text report exchanges between ship captains and third party route providers. It primarily contains information regarding the quality of the suggested routes, such as speed recommendations, safety warnings, and weather forecasts. In total there are 1194 rows with 11 column labels, but not every data row contains information for every label. All the data is contained within a single file.

3.2.1 Exploratory analysis

The text reports provide a summary of communication between the captain of the vessel and the offshore weather routing team. The text data was provided as a formatted CSV file for ease of analysis. In this section, we provide a detailed analysis of the communication reports.

NAME	Description	Non-Null %
SPEED RECOMMENDATION	information about recommended speed for the suggested route	91.46
ROUTE RECOMMENDATION	short description of the recommended route	89.36
WEATHER	description of weather forecast	79.81
REASON	information about why this specific route has been recommended short	10.72
SAFETY WARNING	information about potential safety hazards on the suggested route	4.69
CAPTAIN COMMENT	Captain's response to the weather routers AND/OR comments to suggested route	2.76
OTHER	any other text information	2.43
TROPICAL OUTLOOK	short description of tropical weather forecast	0.92
ROUTE COMPARISON	comparative information about suggested routes (if multiple are provided) OR differences to route suggested by captain	0.83
TROPICAL FORECAST DISCUSSION	long description of tropical weather forecast	0.33
TROPICAL FORECAST CONFIDENCE	forecast's confidence scores	0.17

Table 2: Overview of columns in text report data

The report data consists of 1197 communication records with 11 columns. Table 2 shows a brief description of the columns present in the formatted text report along with the percentage Non-NULL value count for each column. We observe that apart from the *ROUTE RECOMMENDATION*, *SPEED RECOMMENDATION* and *WEATHER*, all other columns are mostly unpopulated.

Figure 6 presents a word cloud of the *ROUTE RECOMMENDATION*, *SPEED RECOMMENDATION*, *REASON*, and *CAPTAIN'S COMMENTS*. We observe that the top three most common words in the route recommendation are: '*route*', '*remains*' and '*valid*'. This suggests that the most common route suggestion is "*route remains valid*". For the speed recommendation, a speed to water (STW) recommendation is provided most commonly along with an estimated time of arrival (ETA). We observe a variety of different reasons provided for the recommendation such as, economy saving, early arrival, and better current etc. However, this information is only available for 10% of the communication records. A similar observation can be made about the captain's comments as well with an even lower number of records populated with this information (< 5%).

Further analysis of the captain's comments reveals that out of the 33 records where the captain's comments are available, only one record has the route recommendation, speed recommendation and reason populated in the report. The key values in the record are shown in the Table 3. In addition, there is only one record with the captain's feedback for the weather update as shown in the Table 4.

4 Approach

The DSG objectives can be divided into two major areas, based on the two datasets. The first focuses on the route voyage data, aiming to identify parts of the route that can best explain why one route deviates from another and to isolate the features that cause performance differences between the different routes.

The second aspect is report generation and evaluation. Using the identified waypoints and isolated features, a summary of this information

Column	Value
ID	1006
ROUTE RECOMMENDATION	Basis Latest weather forecast we have ran the simulation at Constant Speed for RTA. Understood intentions to proceed at 11 knots until Cape Horn and then adjust speed as required on Atlantic side.
REASON	This options indicates better weather factor and improves passage economy by savings of 78.0 metric tonnes of FOC.
SPEED RECOMMENDATION	Simulations at Constant Speed at 7.50 knots STW(average 7.50 knots SOG) for RTA (about 2.0 hours buffer)
WEATHER	NA
SAFETY WARNING	NA
CAPTAIN COMMENT	If we slow down now most recent (about one hour before) weather update shows 6m westerly swell 34 knots west wind at Cape Horn on 25 March and propeller emergence. Swell and wind are following not against but still I prefer to avoid slowing down from 10 knots to 8 knots. It will prolong coastal navigation in an area that can give seriously bad weather. Also an aspect that is not depicted in Route Advice is the actual relation between ordered speed (close to STW) and speed made good (SOG). Right now weather conditions are excellent and Engine rpm translate well into speed. We could slow down after Cape Horn on Atlantic where we may have also some very rough weather. So any distance gain now is to our benefit. New forecast shows that there may be unexpected change of conditions between forecasts as Cape Horn is still over one week away.

Table 3: Record with Captain's feedback on route/speed recommendation

Column	Value
ID	501
ROUTE RECOMMENDATION	NA
SPEED RECOMMENDATION	NA
REASON	NA
WEATHER	Expect Rough seas/ Swell conditions in Strong - Near gale NW'ly winds until 26th AM UTC Followed by subsiding weather conditions.
SAFETY WARNING	NA
CAPTAIN COMMENT	Noted Vessel Still drifting at USWC outside ECA As such we have added delays of about 72.0 Hrs to provide you point weather forecast.

Table 4: Record with captain feedback on weather information

is generated for a ship's captain. The email communications provide examples of what current human reports look like, although the quality of the available data is low. A method for evaluating the generated reports is also explored, as the quality of the reports will significantly impact user trust.

4.1 Research Questions

The three DSG objectives are formulated as four research questions for each sub-team to answer. The first two questions relate to the first objective of isolating important features. The third and fourth questions aim to address the second and third objectives respectively:

1. How can we identify crucial waypoints?
2. How can important features explain the selected route to the ship captains?
3. How can we communicate this information effectively to the ship captain?
4. How can we evaluate an AI-generated report for quality assurance?

The results of each research question leads into the next, creating a

pipeline to the final result. This approach is modular, allowing different methods to be investigated at each stage. Figure 7 shows an overview of the whole process with the methods that were explored.

Figure 7: Processes of the DSG challenge

In the first research question, not every waypoint or feature of a newly suggested route may be crucial for explaining why the route is more efficient. For example, waypoints near the beginning and end of a route may follow strict traffic schemes, while waypoints in open ocean can vary drastically. The first step is to identify which waypoints make the largest difference between two routes. Section 5 investigates how important waypoints can be identified by extracting segments of a fuel-savings optimised route that deviates from a time optimised route. The second research question focuses on explaining the features, ranking them in order of importance. Section 6 takes the identified segments and scores the importance of each feature using linear regression and a random forest on the daily fuel consumption of the vessel.

After identifying important features and waypoints, the data can be used to generate reports and explanations for the ship's captain. The third research question examines how to communicate the feature importance information effectively. Section 7 demonstrates an example of an interactive report system using a retrieval augmented generation (RAG) large language model (LLM) system and a chat bot user interface. Finally the quality of any generated communications need to be evaluated for quality assurance. Section 8 aims to address this question by generating synthetic reports and using a BERT model to classify good and bad reports.

5 Extracting segments of interest along a vessel's route

5.1 Methodology

The genetic algorithm used to optimise shipping routes between any two discrete ports, provides n Pareto-optimal solutions between said ports. Pareto-optimal solutions are the best possible solutions where further improvement on one objective, such as fuel savings, would require a trade-off in another objective, such as travel time. Of these n solutions, we only consider the two extreme situations - the one that provides the greatest fuel savings (MinFuel) and the one that provides the shortest travel time (MinTime).

Figure 8: Vera Cruz to Nouadhibou optimal routes

Figure 8 shows the MinFuel route in red and the MinTime route in blue. We hypothesise that any deviation from the MinTime route will be in an effort to save fuel while losing out on time.

It could be expected that the conditions faced along the MinFuel route are the contributing factors to said fuel savings. As such, the end goal of identifying the causal factors behind choosing one route over another follows the first two research questions; namely first identifying the segments of interest along a vessel's route, and secondly analysing said segments to capture the external factors having the largest impact on route selection.

As Figure 8 shows, there is a clear deviation in the two routes at two

distinct segments: first in the Gulf of Mexico, coming back to the MinTime route around the Bahamas, before diverging again in the second segment stretching across the North Atlantic Ocean. In line with the argument previously presented we would assume factors creating fuel savings to appear in these deviated segments, making it crucial to identify them.

The methodology chosen to extract these segments is to calculate the distance between discrete waypoints on the MinFuel front to the closest point on the MinTime route, treating it as a line instead of its discrete waypoints, helping us identify segments of interest.

While the current methodology only uses the two extremes of the Pareto-optimal set of solutions, the algorithm should be applicable to any of the optimal solutions. In the case of a random solution, the goal would be to either compare it to the MinTime route or the MinFuel route, thereby extracting segments of interest that will help explain the deviation from either front. Deviations from the MinFuel front will explain causal factors as to why a more time-efficient route was chosen and what led to those time-efficiencies, and vice versa for comparisons to the MinTime front.

5.2 Validating Segment Extraction Method

To validate the segment selection method, where the fuel optimised route deviates from the time-optimised route, we looked at two further ship movement metrics. The first utilised the distance the ship covered between consecutive waypoints. A second metric, delta heading, was defined as the change in heading (direction in degrees) of the ship between consecutive waypoints (< 180 degrees).

5.2.1 Results

Figure 9 show the two metrics for the example route from Vera Cruz to Nouadhibou, the MinFuel route in blue and the MinTime route in red. Vertical lines represent the beginning and end of two segments previously identified. The distance (Fig. 9.a) and delta heading (Fig. 9.b) between MinFuel and MinTime routes are equal outside of segments, but deviate within. While the ship movements within the second segment appear

similar for both metrics, the segment is in open ocean where waypoints and the distance between waypoints are typically very consistent. Therefore similar but not identical behaviour is expected between the routes in the second segment. This confirms our choice of method for identifying and selecting segments of diversion in section 5.

Figure 10 shows the average difference in distance and delta heading. As evidenced for both metrics, the distribution of means varies greatly between waypoints in segments (blue) and waypoints outside of identified segments (yellow). Ship movements not in segments of interest for both metrics are close to zero whereas a greater spread is observed for segment movements across all routes. The results show that our method for identifying segments can be generalised across all routes and is supported by both distance and delta heading.

5.3 Discussion and limitations

Outliers can be seen in Figure 9, where a few routes exhibit a high mean difference in distance and heading for parts of the routes classified as not being in the segment of interest. These outliers should be further investigated to understand why the segmentation methodology does not apply well to those routes, whether it is due to specific properties of those routes or if further improvements to the segmentation approach are needed. There are also some minor issues with the segmentation occurring too late. For example, in Figure 9.b, we can see the delta heading of the ships diverge before the start of the second segment is identified at waypoint 30. This could be due to the threshold we set for the distance calculation, which can be better tuned to the dataset.

We suspect that outside the segments, the ships are in confined areas close to shores, where constraints on potential routes exist. Distances of less than 100 kilometres between waypoints are known to signify near-shore movement, which characterises all but two movements between non-segment waypoints. This suggests that within these areas, route options are limited, and deviations are unlikely. In contrast, within the segments, fewer constraints exist, enabling route deviations, and therefore these areas are of greater importance.

5.3.1 Future work

The current segment definition only accounts for divergence in space and does not factor in differences in distance and delta heading. While we have used these metrics to verify our chosen segment definition, they could also be integrated to form a more robust approach.

6 Feature importance

6.1 Methodology

Regarding the second research question, the focus is on analysing the identified segments and determining the important features that can explain the differences in a chosen route. Given that we are working with an optimised route (either for fuel or time efficiency), our objective is to identify which features are most important for saving fuel or time, respectively.

While we do not expect these models to have strong predictive power, a higher feature importance suggests a stronger influence on the optimisation outcome. Therefore, the validation of feature importance relies on white-box validation techniques, such as evaluations by domain experts.

To achieve this, existing features from the voyage route data, along with additional engineered features, are investigated and combined. Several approaches can be considered for determining feature importance, such as Random Forests (RF), which have been shown to be effective for inverse modelling ([3]).

Two separate machine learning models are tested: linear regression and random forests. The methodology involves fitting the machine learning models to each segment and obtaining a quantifiable measure of the importance of each feature. Although the two models use slightly different features to obtain feature importance scores, the overall approach remains the same.

6.1.1 Feature Engineering

The voyage route data contains weather information at specific points in time and location, which is unique to each waypoint. The goal is to provide a set of features that explain why the fuel-optimised route deviates from the time-optimised route.

During the segment identification process, a flag has been added to indicate whether a waypoint from the fuel-optimised route deviates from the time-optimised route. Additionally, these deviations have been segmented into different parts. Information on the extent of the deviation and the potential fuel and time savings between the two routes is reported.

The feature engineering step is two-fold. First, we need to determine which predictive features to include in our model. The following are the features we have selected for the linear regression:

- **Wave height:** The higher the waves, the more it will hurt the progress of the vessel and it will need to use more fuel to reach the target speed.
- **Wind speed:** The strength of the wind will impact the vessel negatively if it sails against it, or positively if it sails with it.
- **Ocean current speed:** The strength of the ocean current will impact the vessel in the same way as the wind speed.
- **Wind direction:** If the wind is blowing in the same direction as the vessel is heading, then it will positively impact its fuel consumption.
- **Wave direction:** It will have the same effect as the wind direction.
- **Ocean current direction:** It will have the same effect as the wind direction.
- **ECA zone:** Passing through an Emission Controlled Area means that a vessel is restricted in the type of fuel it can use, and will have to use more expensive, less environmentally-harmful fuel.

Some notable omissions from the list of features that were provided:

- **Speed:** Target speed is mostly constant over fuel-optimised routes.

- **Wave period:** Wave period is determined by the wave height.

For the random forest model, additional features were included, including some that were omitted from the linear regression model. These additional features were added because the random forest model is not sensitive to correlations between variables, allowing more possible features:

- **Vessel heading:** The absolute heading of the vessel in degrees to show the direction of the vessel.
- **Wave period:** The period of the waves will impact how often the vessel makes contact with a wave, potentially slowing down the vessel.
- **Ocean current speed:** The strength of the ocean current can impact the speed and fuel consumption of the vessel, negatively when sailing against it, or positively when sailing with it.

The second step is to compute flags for specific events. This can be used for the report generation to emphasise the important events or characteristics of a waypoint. There are three specific binary flags used:

- **Open water:** A ship is considered in open water if the distance of a waypoint to the next waypoint is larger than 100km (54 nautical miles).
- **Safety scores:** How close is the current wind speed, wave height and vessel speed to the maximum threshold for this vessel.
- **Sharp changes:** Sudden change, compared to the previous waypoint, in vessel speed and direction, wind speed and direction, wave direction and height, ocean current direction and speed close is the current wind speed, wave height and vessel speed to the maximum threshold for this vessel.

Finally, we also added route specific information which is useful for filtering and context. This includes the name of the vessel, loading conditions, departure and arrival port, and the type of optimised routes.

A full data dictionary was created which includes a very detailed description of each feature and flag (whether used in the predictive models or not). This is crucial information to pass onto the report

generation step, to communicate what each feature means and the context of the current route, segment or waypoint.

6.1.2 Linear Regression

We devised a strategy to infer the relevant features that characterise the waypoints in segments of interest. The goal is to understand the impact of the weather conditions on the choice of the route. We fitted a linear regression model for each segment considering seven different features:

1. the wave height
2. the wind speed,
3. the ocean current speed,
4. the difference in wind direction,
5. the wind direction difference,
6. the wave direction difference
7. the ocean current direction difference

For each route, we first scaled the features using a `RobustScaler`, a preprocessing step in the `sklearn` library which maintains the distribution of the data by scaling the data using the quantiles. The importance of the segments were quantified by fitting a regressor on the dependent variable `dailyFuelConsumption` considering the seven features described above.

Feature importance per segment is summarised by the coefficients inferred via the linear model, which describe the impact of the weather features on the fuel consumption at the segment granularity: these coefficients provide local information on the weather condition.

6.1.3 Random Forests

Random forests are an ensemble learning method that build on bootstrapping decision trees and selecting the average of all predictions from these randomly split trees [1].

Since the features are selected for each tree based on the minimal impurity (Gini impurity), the features itself usually do not need to be normalised. However, when the features have significantly different scales and the model is used for feature importance rather than prediction, as is in our case, some form of normalisation is advised [9].

In our analysis we applied Min-Max normalisation to scale the features to the range [0,1] and calculated as,

$$x' = a + \frac{(x - \min(x))(b - a)}{\max(x) - \min(x)}$$

where a, b are the minimum and maximum values, x is the original value and x' is the scaled.

We employed the scikit-learn package [8] to build the RF model, opting for 100 trees. This number is large enough to yield the best possible results, while simultaneously not being exhaustive computationally.

The features selected for the RF model are slightly different from those for the linear regression, as this model is not sensitive to correlations between variables, and the algorithm itself tests the variance when a variable is removed to assess the impact it has.

The built-in entropy-based feature importance function from scikit-learn was utilised to assess the effects of the variables on the specified route for the given optimisation objective (i.e., minimising daily fuel consumption or duration).

To demonstrate the impact of different features on each waypoint of interest, we assigned a relative importance to each feature at individual waypoints by multiplying the overall importance scores by the feature values at each waypoint. This approach assumes that the overall importance is indicative of the feature's contribution across the entire route, and that this contribution is consistent at each waypoint. This method is applied to both the entire route and each segment individually.

We also tested the changes that occur when we examine the segments flagged as divergent from the time efficiency route together and built an

RF model based on them. For instance, in our example of a fuel-optimised route, three segments were identified: segment zero, where there is no divergence from the other extreme solution, and segments one and two, where divergence was observed. So we built a model for comparison on the whole route, on each segment, and on the joint segments of one and two.

6.2 Results

6.2.1 Linear regression

We performed the linear regression analysis on the whole dataset at the segment level: for each segment, we fitted a multi-variate linear regression model quantifying feature importance using seven features as previously described in Section 6.1.2. The coefficients inferred by the model quantify the importance of each feature on daily fuel consumption and thus strong negative values suggest features that reduce fuel consumption, and vice versa strong positive coefficients increase fuel consumption.

Figure 11 shows the feature importance (coefficients) for one route, considering the vessel (9999982) with ballast loading on the route from Vera Cruz to Nouadhibou optimised for fuel efficiency. Segments have different weather characteristics overall, the wave height being the most relevant feature for all the three segments.

Segment one seems to be the most impacted by weather conditions, with strong positive weight for the wave height and wind direction difference. This suggests that wave height increases fuel consumption, for example in segment one, whereas wind direction difference decreases fuel consumption.

6.2.2 Random Forests

Using the same voyage of the vessel (9999982) with ballast loading on the route from Vera Cruz to Nouadhibou optimised for fuel efficiency, the random forest results can be observed in Figure 12. Three segments are identified for this route containing waypoints of interest. The feature importance scores are compared on the whole route (blue), segment zero (red), where there is no divergence from the other extreme solution,

segments one (green) and two (purple), where divergence was observed, and on the joint segments of one and two (yellow). The results of the joint segments of one and two are interesting as these two segments contain waypoints that diverge from the time-optimised route.

In this particular route, segment zero has 32 data points, segment one has 9, and segment two has 23, while the joint segments one and two have 31.

Similar to the results for the Linear Regression, wave heights are shown to have the most significant effect on fuel savings. This is clearly the case for segment two, but also applies to other routes when we discount the features that have been combined in that model.

Direction appears to be the most important variable when considering the whole route, and this primarily stems from its effect on the non-divergent route segment. Table 5 highlights the waypoint-level feature importance derived from the three most significant attributes. This could potentially offer insights into why a particular waypoint is considered the most fuel-efficient.

6.3 Discussion and limitations

The methodology used here serves as an initial approximation, allowing us to quantify and compare the impact of features at different stages of the route. By summing the calculated feature importance values for each waypoint, we obtain a composite score that reflects the cumulative influence of all features at that specific point. This aggregate score can be interpreted as the waypoint's overall contribution to the route's optimisation objective. However, it assumes that each feature's importance is additive and that their combined effect can be quantified as a single metric. While this simplifies the complex interactions between features, it provides a practical means to gauge the relative significance of each waypoint within the context of the entire route.

Since the segments of interest vary in size and length, we would expect that the performance of the model vary based on the data considered: the weather conditions of segments with very few waypoints, far away in the ocean, might not be very accurate. Similarly, weather features of segments

Waypoint position	Top three most important features
15	windDirection [deg], windU [m/s], oceanCurrentSpeed [m/s]
16	windSpeed [m/s], waveHeight [m], wavePeriod [s]
17	waveHeight [m], windDirection [deg], windSpeed [m/s]
18	waveHeight [m], windSpeed [m/s], windDirection [deg]
19	waveHeight [m], windDirection [deg], windSpeed [m/s]
21	oceanCurrentSpeed [m/s], oceanCurrentDirection [deg], oceanCurrentU [m/s]
22	oceanCurrentDirection [deg], oceanCurrentSpeed [m/s], oceanCurrentU [m/s]
23	oceanCurrentSpeed [m/s], oceanCurrentDirection [deg], windU [m/s]
24	oceanCurrentDirection [deg], oceanCurrentSpeed [m/s], windU [m/s]

Table 5: Top three features for each waypoint in segment one on the example route, as determined by the Random Forest model

with many waypoints might not be captured by a simple linear model, since weather conditions might be heterogeneous in those big segments.

The choice of linear regression is justified by the number of waypoints: we have few waypoints within many of the segments as shown in Figure 13. Similarly, the random forest model is chosen to potentially gain more information as a larger and more complex model. There are a few sets of segments with over 120 waypoints, which may be more suited to a random forest compared to a linear regression model. The models do not aim to predict new data points, the purpose is just to explain the contribution of each feature we observe, i.e. we just fit a line and extract the coefficient values. Hence, we do not need a test set. We have a median R^2 score of 0.408 on the linear regression model, and 0.884 on the random forest model, suggesting the random forest model is able to provide a much better fit compared to the linear regression model.

6.3.1 Future work

Both the linear regression and random forest model are used and tested separately. A good way to assess and validate their results would be to compare the feature importance scores obtained via RF compared to the simpler linear regression model. We can then see if certain feature importance scores match from both models, and if there are significant differences on which routes do they occur in. This could inform us which model works best for what kind of route or segment, and an ensemble method consisting of multiple models can be built.

One way to make the metrics more robust is to perform a test on each feature individually, recording the impact on the overall importance scores by varying (both increasing and decreasing) a feature's value by certain percentages, while keeping all other variables constant. Furthermore, the primary validation of these models' performance relies on white-box validation techniques, such as evaluations by domain experts. Therefore, the developed model alternatives need to be evaluated on a route-by-route basis by domain experts.

7 Interactive routing report system

The proposed LLM-based system aims to provide a static report similar to the reports the captain currently receives from the ship router. Furthermore, in order to build further trust with the captain, the system allows follow-up questions to be posed by the user. This allows the captain to query the underlying data and request further details about specific waypoints for example, the captain might ask "what is the weather like at the next waypoint?"

To achieve this, a pipeline based on a Large Language Model (LLM) was devised. Specifically a Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) pipeline was used. RAG allows an LLM to pull data from an associated data store. Major steps in the RAG pipeline can be summarised as:

1. Construct an embedded vector store of meta data which describe the contents of the DataFrame. The DataFrame contains the values and importance weightings of each feature.
2. Prompt the LLM to generate pandas queries to retrieve data.
3. Retrieved data is then used to generate written reports with the same LLM.
4. Follow-up questions can then be asked on the generated report.

7.1 Methodology

7.1.1 Input data for the RAG LLM system

For a RAG LLM system to function, the first step is to provide data as part of the vector store. The data can be later fetched by the LLM to ensure accurate generation.

We provided the RAG LLM with three main sets of data:

- A Pandas DataFrame of waypoints and their features.
- A written description of the DataFrame and its columns.

The Pandas DataFrame contains the raw values of the features at each waypoint, and the importance weighting of each feature. The written

description of this DataFrame describes the overall structure of the data, description of what each columns of the DataFrame means, and measurement units of the values in the columns. This written description provides additional context for the LLM, as the initial testing without any description led to irrelevant outputs by the LLM in response to user queries.

7.1.2 Large Language Model setup

The following system prompt is used for the LLM to generate the initial report:

SYSTEM PROMPT: you are giving responses to a ship captain about the prescribed route for an upcoming voyage based on different metrics provided in the data. Abide by the following guidelines about communicating with the captain:

For language model itself, the Mixtral 8x7b model [4] was selected for its speed and performance. This model was run using the Groq API and Llama Index was used as the data framework. The underlying model and framework can be easily exchanged with any other local model such as Llama 3 [5] or an API-based model such as OpenAI's GPT-4 [6].

A Pandas Query Engine was integrated which uses an LLM to generate Python code from natural language inputs when the user submits a query referring to data which needs to be retrieved from the DataFrame.

Memory was included in the system by passing the conversation history back to the LLM as part of the prompt with any new queries.

7.1.3 User Interface

A simple front-end UI was built using Streamlit to first present the user with the initial report and then allow the user to query the underlying data used to generate the report through a chat interface, as shown in Figure 15.

7.2 Results

The model outputs were validated by comparing the intermediate dataset filtered by the model to the ground truth information for the sample of waypoints. We tested the model's performance with the queries "Find the coordinates of the ship's position" (expected to output numerical values), "Is there a sharp change in wind speed?" (expected to output True/False), and "What is the temperature today?" (an irrelevant question that should not produce any output). The model successfully passed all tests.

The system successfully retrieved accurate data from the provided DataFrame demonstrating the success of the RAG approach. However, at times the LLM would not completely fulfill the chatbot queries, for example returning different data than what was requested, suggesting that further prompt engineering is required. The result is determined qualitatively from reading the responses from the LLM. A better quantitative metric would require improved datasets with back and forth conversations between the ship captain and the human reporting team, to provide ground truth data for comparison.

The overall structure of the chat bot implementation, with an initial report followed by natural language querying functionality, was seen as a successful concept. The initial report provided a baseline level of information of a similar standard to that currently received by the ship captain from other routing providers based on our own qualitative observations, whereas the chat bot extended this to allow for further detail on the important metrics and data based on the feature importance scores.

7.3 Discussion and limitations

An LLM RAG-based system was implemented using feature importance scores and a data dictionary to provide accurate responses and reports. The LLM is able to generate an initial report and answer follow up questions, but it does not always return the relevant information or answers to the follow up questions.

The advantage of using an LLM system is to allow an open approach for captains to respond and communicate back to the language model,

forming a dialogue to allow captains to ask further question or more clarifications on the reasons for the chosen route. Additionally, a captain can respond and provide a description of what they've done, such as if and why they did or did not follow the provided route, and the conversation that can be used as data in the future for testing the model performance.

However, there are several limitations with the LLM approach. First, the major limitation is the lack of understanding of the user queries. Although the model can retrieve data present in the DataFrame, it does not always retrieve the data which the user has requested, signalling a lack of understanding of the data and column names, despite being provided a data dictionary. Further, the RAG approach contains fewer guard rails compared to a fine tuning approach, or a stricter non-LLM approach. Because the LLM in a RAG approach comes out-of-the-box, it can be derailed and asked unrelated questions. Using a fine tuning approach does not solve all these problems as it is complicated, requiring a large high quality dataset for training. We investigate and discuss the need for high quality data based on the email communications later in Section 8.

7.3.1 Future work

There are many aspects of the LLM system that can be improved upon, such as prompt engineering, using few-shot examples, fine-tuning, or trying different language models. All methods of improvement will require some form of evaluation, which is partly explored in the next section. Another useful test is to bring in ship captains for a workshop or usability study, gather valuable feedback to then evaluate on improvement methods.

Due to the limitations of the LLM approach, and the long process required for improving the evaluation and data quality, other approaches should also be considered and tested. For example, a report template that uses the feature importance scores and presents the most important features at each waypoint can be a quick prototype. Although such a template will lack the dynamic responses of an LLM, it can ensure accurate and consistent outputs. A further step may be to use a context-free grammar approach.

8 Evaluating Generated Reports

While the initial report given to the captain is well-structured, we hope to give a report that can be tailored to each captain or be able to generate dynamic reports based on the current conditions. In this section, we discuss how this can be done with the report data that is communicated to the captain. This work is not actually implemented with the LLM because of the scarcity of high quality data, discussed in Section 3.2.1. We instead generate some synthetic data of email reports to evaluate how a BERT model can classifying good reports and bad reports, noting that training will yield better results with sufficient communication data.

8.1 Methodology

8.1.1 Identifying good reports from bad reports in data

We propose the following three metrics to quantify the quality of a report:

- **Non-null field count:** Since the CSV data structures the text data into designated columns, we can leverage this data to identify what kind of information is available within the report by looking at the columns that are populated (Non-NULL) within each report.
- **Token count:** Having non-null values in the fields is not an indicator of the depth of content in a field. Therefore, we also count how many tokens are present within each field.
- **Content quality score:** Finally, the overall quality, relevance and depth of information in each field can be evaluated by evaluating a similarity score with respect to a reference corpus.

For a report to be considered good, all three metrics should be above their corresponding threshold value. Note that from the email communications, it is very rare for every field to be populated as noted in Section 3.2.1 and Table 2. Thus, we discard fields with less than 2.5% non-null percentage count leaving us with a total of six fields: *route recommendation*, *speed recommendation*, *weather*, *reason*, *safety warning*, and *captain comment*. Therefore, the above metrics are evaluated only for the six selected fields

as mentioned. The thresholds for the first two metrics are assigned as follows,

- **Non-null field count:** at least four of the selected fields should be non-null
- **Token count:** each field should have at least three tokens

To assess content quality and establish a threshold for the metric, we need reference data comprising high-quality text from previous email communications between the captain and the weather routing team. Note that it does not have to be email data, any reference data such as previous reports could be used for reference. Due to the lack of good-quality reference data, we generate synthetic data using some handpicked good-quality examples (records that meet the first two criteria) from the data. After filtering through all the text data for good examples, we are left with 112 samples. These samples will be used to guide the creation of synthetic data using an LLM model. Note that this LLM (GPT-4o) is different from the model used for natural language conversations with the captain.

8.1.2 Synthetic reference data generation

One important goal of the synthetic data is to have each data sample as unique as possible. In order to do that, we want to have a high variability between the examples that the LLM will see before producing the synthetic data. To figure out which of the samples have the most variability between them, we do a pairwise BERTScore [10] calculation between all the good samples of text data. The BERTScore calculates how similar two pieces of text are using cosine similarity on the BERT embeddings. BERTScore is effective because it uses BERT's contextual understanding unlike other methods such as BLEU, ROGUE, etc. that use n-grams to calculate similarity.

The process to select the most unique text data is as follows:

1. The pair (x, y) with the lowest BERTScore is added to the list of examples to keep.
2. Calculate the BERTScore of each text with x and y . The one with the lowest sum of BERTScores is then added to the list as a 3rd

example.

3. Iteratively do this with the growing list until the list is of sufficient size (up to the user).

We do this for five iterations as the BERTScores after this become high, meaning most of the examples are already similar. With the list of examples, we now give this to an LLM to produce more examples. The LLM is given the structure of the report and the list of examples and is asked to generate more synthetic examples. With this method, we double the size of good example text data. We do not produce more than this because the majority of positive examples would be synthetic which we wish to avoid.

Now that there exists a corpus of synthetic data that simulates good emails, we can match the real data we have to the synthetic data to see the quality of *all* the real emails. The main idea is that the good-quality emails should have a high similarity score with the synthetic data whereas the poor-quality emails would have a lower similarity score. To see how well this does, we use the BLEU score [7] metric to calculate how similar an email response is to the corpus of synthetic data. The BLEU score works by building n-grams between the original text and reference text and computing similarity. We will show how well this does with the current data, but in the future, this will be used to evaluate an LLM-generated report.

Figure 16 shows a histogram of the BLEU score evaluated for all records in the data against the synthetic corpus of high-quality text data generated using the LLM (GPT-4o) model. The red vertical line is the chosen threshold for the content quality metric (BLEU score). Reports with a BLEU score value greater than or equal to the threshold (0.28) along with the minimum populated field count and token count (as discussed in the previous section) are assigned the high-quality label. The threshold was chosen at a score higher than the median BLEU score to ensure higher quality data, but not so high to maintain a balance of low and high-quality labels in the dataset. After assigning the binary class label for report quality, we are left with following report counts by class:

Quality	Count
Good	231
Bad	963

Table 6: Number of good and bad quality reports based on assigned metrics

8.2 BERT for classification of report quality

The objective of generating data with binary labels for quality is to train a model capable of capturing the underlying context features from the data. Therefore, we fine-tune a pre-trained BERT model for the classification problem formulated in the previous sections. We use pre-trained weights from ‘bert-uncased-base’ which is the base BERT [2] model pre-trained on uncased data. On top of the BERT encoder, we add two additional fully connected layers with 128 neurons to perform the classification task.

Note that the data is highly imbalanced for the two classes. Therefore, we utilise a weighted cross entropy loss function to train the model. The weights for the classes are computed using the function available in the *scikit-learn* package. The calculated weights are: $w_{good} = 2.58$ and $w_{bad} = 0.62$

8.2.1 Experiment setting and results

We split the labelled data into train and validation sets keeping 80% records for model training and the rest for model validation. The model is trained for 20 epochs using the AdamW optimiser with a learning rate of $lr = 2 \times 10^{-5}$

Table 7 summarises the classification performance of the fine-tuned BERT model on validation data. The model shows an overall accuracy of 92% on the validation data. The F1 score results show that the model is able to generate quality predictions with reasonable accuracy. However, there is a discrepancy in precision, recall and F1 score between the good and the bad labels. The imbalance in the number of data samples available for each class explains this difference in performance for the two classes.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Bad Quality	0.96	0.94	0.95	197
Good Quality	0.74	0.81	0.77	42
accuracy			0.92	239
macro avg	0.85	0.87	0.86	239
weighted avg	0.92	0.92	0.92	239

Table 7: Text quality classification performance on the validation data generated by the scikit-learn classification report

8.3 Discussion and future work

We conducted an experiment where, after using BERTScore for synthetic data generation, the data was divided into good-quality and bad-quality reports using the BLEU score. A BERT model was then trained to classify the good and bad reports, achieving a fairly high F1 score.

While the model performs well, there are a few factors to consider. The synthetic data generation relied on identifying high variability within the current dataset and selecting examples that were the most different, based on BERTScore. However, this may not be the best metric, as the pairwise BERTScores across the entire dataset still indicated high similarity. In fact, the most dissimilar pair had a score of 0.78, suggesting they were still quite similar. We should consider different metrics in future when evaluating variability in the dataset. The same applies to using BLEU score for dividing the dataset between good and bad-quality emails.

Recall that the main reason synthetic data was generated in the first place was due to the lack of quality email data. The synthetic data generation step could be skipped if there were a method to sufficiently collect all email communications, creating a much larger dataset. With a larger, high-quality dataset, the BERT model should theoretically be able to classify good and bad reports with greater accuracy, and the LLM could generate reports in a more dynamic, tailored fashion to meet the needs of the ship’s captain.

Future work would involve the following ideas:

- **Assess different metrics for classifying between good and bad email communications** - Gathering good and bad classifications from user studies can help greatly improve any classification metric, rather than only rely on word and token level scores, to directly gain feedback from human experts.
- **Using good-quality email data to fine-tune an LLM for report generation**

9 Conclusion

A number of approaches and ideas were investigated during the DSG to address the objectives described in Section 2.2. The work was split into four sub-sections to answer the four research questions in Section 4.1. Each piece of work found some interesting results, providing an initial direction to solve different parts of the challenge. Future work can be done to further test the methods explored in the DSG in order to draw more robust conclusions.

9.1 How can we identify crucial waypoints?

The key waypoints of optimised routes are automatically extracted into segments using a distance calculation. This calculation considers two routes: one optimised route and a second standard route for comparison. The fuel-optimised and time-optimised routes serve as the extreme examples of the solution space. The method is validated by calculating the average heading and distance between each waypoint. We find that waypoints identified as segments of interest show a large spread in the average difference in distance and heading, compared to waypoints not in segments of interest, where the average distance is close to zero. The difference in the spread of results between identified waypoints in segments and those not in segments validates the accuracy of the segment identification method.

Although the distance and heading validate most of the identified segments, there are a few anomalies in the results. Future work should focus on investigating these outliers to understand what kinds of voyages

cause the outlying behaviour. Understanding the outliers can help improve the method for identifying segments and ensure that all important segments of a voyage are included.

9.2 How can important features explain the selected route to the ship captains?

From the identified segments of interest, features in the dataset at each identified waypoint are used to train linear regression and random forest models. Additional feature engineering is performed to filter and include secondary flags such as open water, safety scores, and sharp changes. Rather than predicting future waypoints, the models are used to extract importance scores for each feature.

There is no test set for the trained models, as predictive power is not the focus; however, validating the approach is still necessary. Future work should first compare and contrast the linear regression and random forest models. Do both models provide similar feature importance scores? If not, are there particular voyages where the model scores diverge? Identifying the properties of each model in relation to the properties of the voyages can lay the groundwork for an ensemble method of models, where multiple models are used and compared to ensure consistent feature importance scores across different voyages.

9.3 How can we communicate this information effectively to the ship captain?

The feature importance scores are passed into a RAG LLM system with a full data dictionary describing each feature. While the model can retrieve and output data according to the provided information, it does not fully grasp the meaning behind the queries. Additional fine-tuning or prompt engineering strategies could be applied to improve the model's responses. However, other non-LLM approaches, such as a static text template or context-free grammars, should be tested before further work on LLMs is pursued. Gathering feedback from users, such as ship captains, would be invaluable for assessing the quality of generated reports and could serve as training data if an LLM-based approach is continued.

9.4 How can we evaluate an AI-generated report for quality assurance?

Using the text-based BLEU score and a BERT model, the classification of good and bad reports was achieved with high precision and recall. A high accuracy of 92% was reported on the validation data, demonstrating the robustness of the model. However, there are two main limitations to this result. First, the classification is binary, with only 'good' and 'bad' labels, while realistic, detailed reports may require more nuanced classifications. Second, synthetic data was used as part of the dataset due to the lack of high-quality reports from the email dataset, so it is not the best representation of actual human reports.

It is recommended to collect more high-quality email communications to improve both report generation and evaluation. This data collection should include ship captains' responses where possible. A captain's response to a human-generated report provides clarity on the quality of the report, serving as ground truth. In cases where a captain's response does not clearly indicate the report's quality, sentiment analysis can be performed on the responses, and more classifications could be applied based on clustering of the data.

10 Team members

10.1 Participants

Thomas Adler is a PhD Student at Tsinghua University in Beijing, specialising in brain-inspired complex network science for AI. He contributed to this project by developing the features for the explainability model and supporting the segmentation algorithm.

Rashid Barket is a PhD student at Coventry University specialising in machine learning applications for mathematical problems and part of the Applied Skills team at The Alan Turing Institute. He contributed to this project by generating synthetic email data and helping with evaluating the BERT model.

Zsofia Baruwa is a PhD student at the University of Kent, and her

research focuses on the process of transitioning towards the future of transportation, with particular emphasis on the human aspects that can be mined from Social Media. She contributed to this project by establishing the feature importance metrics using the Random Forest method.

Jayati Deshmukh is a Postdoctoral Researcher at the University of Southampton. She is a part of the UKRI Trustworthy Autonomous Systems (TAS Hub), Responsible AI UK (RAI UK) and Citizen-Centric AI Systems (CCAIS) teams. Her research interests are multi-agent systems, responsible AI, network science and game theory. She contributed to this project by estimating the safety metrics of the ship routes and finding the overall feature importance using PCA.

Maciej Glowacki is a particle physics PhD student at the University of Bristol and CERN, specialising in ultra low latency machine learning inference on dedicated hardware accelerators. He contributed to this project by building the report generating autonomous agent centred around Large Language Models and retrieval augmented generation.

Arpit Kapoor is a PhD student at the University of New South Wales, Sydney, specialising in machine learning for modelling physical processes in environmental sciences and hydrology. He contributed to this project by analysing and processing text communication data and training and evaluating the BERT model for the classification of text data.

Chris Ryan is a PhD student at University College London, specialising in naval architecture and maritime engineering. He contributed to his project by implementing the large language model and system prompts for report generation.

David Scott is a PhD student at the University of Liverpool specialising in theoretical ecology. He contributed to this project by validating the segment selection algorithm and calculating the fuel saving per segment. Further contributions were made in formulating the explainability model.

Chittrak Sen is an Analyst at NATS with a background in reinforcement and adversarial learning. He contributed to this project by creating the segmentation algorithm and supporting the explainability modelling.

Francesco Terenzi is a PhD student at the Barts Cancer Institute, Queen Mary University of London, specialising in mathematical modelling applied to biology, specifically in cancer and ageing. He contributed to this project by implementing one of the models for explainability and by supporting the segmentation algorithm.

Artem Volgin is a PhD student at the University of Manchester. He specialises in behavioural and financial data for marketing, non-profit, and academia. He contributed to this project by creating the large language model pipeline with retrieval augmented generation.

10.2 Principal Investigator

Sizhe Yuen is a researcher in the Data-Centric Engineering group at the Alan Turing Institute. His work focuses on the automation of data engineering and machine learning pipelines. His PhD at the University of Southampton specialises in genetic algorithms.

10.3 Challenge Owners

David Young is the CEO and founder of Theyr. With a background in business, he initially worked for shipping companies in Dublin before moving to London. At Theyr, David pursues a lifelong passion in the ocean, to shape and improve the environment with cutting edge digital technologies.

Dr Przemyslaw Grudniewski is a Senior Applied Scientist at Theyr Ltd. He is responsible for the creation and improvement of AI-based solutions within T-VOS voyage optimisation module and integration of vessel digital twins.

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Figure 5: PCA of features for a single route

(a) Average difference in distance

(b) Average difference in heading

Figure 10: Average difference in distance and heading for all routes.

Figure 11: Feature importance score inferred with the linear regression model for vessel 9999982, load Ballast, route Vera Cruz to Nouadhibou.

Feature Importances for the example: 9999982_Ballast_Vera_Cruz_to_Nouadhibou_MIN_FUEL

Figure 12: Feature importance scores gained with the Random Forest regression model for vessel 9999982, with ballast load, on the route from Vera Cruz to Nouadhibou. s0, s1, and s2 refer to each segment, with s12 referring to the joint segments for segment one and two.

Figure 13: Distribution of the number of waypoints within the each segment of interest.

Figure 14: RAG based LLM pipeline for interactive report generation.

Ship Captain Assistant

Ask questions about ship routing.

Areas of significant deviation

Segment 1

Report for segment: Segment 1

Waypoint: 1

Overview:

Position of vessel: (22.2207, -91.6783), Speed of vessel: 10.999975, Deviation from time optimised route: Yes

Important Metrics:

wind_direction_difference windSpeed oceanCurrentSpeed

Ask follow up:

what is weather like here?

Figure 15: UI screenshot

Figure 16: Histogram of BLEU score value of all records in the dataset computed against the synthetic reference data

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